

RMP-001: Requirements Management Plan

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Abbreviations

- | | |
|---|---|
| AAAI : Authentication, Authorization, and Accounting Infrastructure. | RE : Requirements Engineering |
| ACL : Access Control List. | PR : Pull Request. |
| CaC : Compliance as Code. | RACI : Responsible, Accountable, Consulted, and Informed. |
| CI/CD : Continuous Integration / Continuous Deployment. | RATM : Requirement Adoption Traceability Matrix. |
| CR : Change Request. | ReqIF : Requirements Interchange Format. |
| DAC : Data Access Committee. | RMP : Requirements Management Plan. |
| DPIA : Data Protection Impact Assessment. | SATRE : Standardised Architecture for Trusted Research Environments. |
| DSA : Data Sharing Agreement. | SDC : Statistical Disclosure Control. |
| DUA : Data Use Agreement. | SGE : System-Generated Evidence. |
| GDPR : General Data Protection Regulation. | SLA : Service Level Agreement. |
| GRC : Governance, Risk and Compliance. | SOP : Standard Operating Procedure. |
| IaC : Infrastructure as Code. | SWOT : Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats. |
| MFA : Multi-Factor Authentication. | SyRS : System Requirement Specification. |
| OSCAL : Open Security Controls Assessment Language. | TRE : Trusted Research Environm |
| OTPF : Open TRE Provider Forum. | |

1. Purpose

This Requirements Management Plan (RMP) defines the structured methodology used in EOSC-ENTRUST to elicit, analyse, validate, register, and maintain requirements for federated Trusted Research Environments (TREs). It establishes a consistent and traceable approach to transform stakeholder needs into managed requirements suitable for version control, cross-TRE structured comparison, and long-term governance.

The RMP serves as a methodological framework for requirements engineering within the project. It supports requirements quality, transparency and interoperability across heterogeneous TRE contexts, as well as adherence to EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint architectural principles. Still, the document does not prescribe organisational models, operational controls or implementations, nor establish compliance or certification obligations. Yet, evidence-based traceability is introduced as a methodological mechanism to assess requirement scope and verifiability. As such, it provides the basis for future alignment with external assurance, audit, or certification schemes.

The RMP is designed for use by project partners, TRE operators, and federation governance bodies, although it is designed to remain applicable beyond its duration. The framework and artefacts defined herein prioritise low-maintenance, open, and reusable approaches, enabling continued use and evolution under community-driven structures such as the Open TRE Provider Forum (OTPF).

2. Objectives and Scope

This RMP defines the methodological and analytical framework used in EOSC-ENTRUST to systematically manage requirements applicable to Trusted Research Environments (TREs) or federation of TREs. It specifies the what, why, and where of requirements management within the project, and establishes a foundation for traceability, quality, and interoperability.

Objectives

The objectives of this RMP are to:

- **Establish a structured methodology** for eliciting, consolidating and managing requirements for TREs within EOSC-ENTRUST.
- **Enable comparison and alignment** across heterogeneous TRE contexts enforcing normalization, traceability and registration of requirements through controlled vocabulary artefacts and a lightweight governance model.
- **Ensure long-term usability and sustainability** of requirements beyond the EOSC-ENTRUST project lifecycle.
- **Provide a basis for future assurance activities** by structuring requirements in a way that supports evidence-based assessment, audit readiness and potential alignment with certification or automated assurance frameworks.

Scope

This RMP covers requirements with technical, operational, legal, ethical, and governance implications for TREs and TRE federations. It covers the full requirements lifecycle, including:

- elicitation of requirements from Drivers, use cases, and community input;
- consolidation, clarification, and traceability screening of requirements;
- registration, versioning, and maintenance of requirement definitions;
- assessment and verification means through evidence-based traceability.

The RMP defines processes, roles, and structured artefacts to support these activities. It does not mandate specific tools or technical implementations, but ensures that requirements are expressed and maintained in a manner compatible with recognised standards and future interoperability needs.

3. Guiding Principles

To ensure the framework remains reusable and sustainable beyond the project lifecycle, the following principles guide all requirements management activities:

- **Transparency and Accountability:** all requirements are traceable to their source, interpretation, and lifecycle status. Decisions related to clarification, screening, or change are explicitly documented to ensure accountability and reproducibility.
- **Interoperability:** Requirements and related artefacts are expressed using open, vendor-neutral representations (e.g. JSON, ReqIF-compatible models) to enable reuse, exchange, and long-term accessibility beyond the project.
- **Low-Maintenance design:** the framework favours low-maintenance processes, lightweight governance, and minimal tooling, relying on version control and human-readable artefacts.
- **Community-driven:** requirements management is informed by contributions from Drivers, TRE providers, and relevant project stakeholders. The framework supports collaborative review, commentary, and prioritisation without centralised control.
- **Controlled Evolution:** requirements changes are managed through lightweight versioning and review cycles via Git, preserving traceability and historical context while avoiding unnecessary overhead.
- **Audit Readiness:** requirements are structured to enable future use in audit, assurance or certification contexts by supporting evidence-based traceability and clear responsibility attribution.
- **Automation Awareness:** the conceptual model considers potential future automation of evidence and assessment (*i.e.* Compliance-as-Code).
- **Framework Alignment:** requirements are analysed in relation to existing standards and frameworks (e.g. ENTRUST Blueprint).

4. Standards Alignment

This section provides an introduction to the reference standards that govern the processes, data structures, and quality criteria within this RMP. It is designed to be compatible with international specifications for business logics, requirements exchange, automation, and structure. This ensures that the requirements managed within the project remain interoperable with professional Requirements Engineering (RE) tools and emerging Compliance-as-Code (CaC) ecosystems. The model specifically aligns with three primary pillars:

- ISO/IEC/IEEE 29148 (*i.e.* ISO 29148)¹ for requirements lifecycle, metadata content and controlled vocabulary
- Requirement Interchange Format (ReqIF)² for requirements interoperability
- Open Security Controls Assessment Language (OSCAL)³ for assessment logic

4.1 ISO/IEC/IEEE 29148:2018

ISO29148 is the international standard that provides a unified set of processes, document templates and quality characteristics for engineering requirements throughout the life cycle of systems and software products. To ensure that requirements are actionable, manageable and verifiable, this RMP adopts the standard in different dimensions:

Process Life Cycle

The transition from stakeholder elicitation to system validation maps directly to the Requirements Engineering Process described in the standard, ensuring a systematic approach across the TRE federation when producing, managing and tracking the requirements. [Section 5](#) describes the entire cycle in detail and [Appendix A: Glossary](#) adopts their terminology.

Data model

To make requirements actionable and manageable, [section 7](#) proposes a minimal set of interrelated object definitions that facilitate and fully support the application of the normative practices: requirements identification, traceability, verifiability, etc. The “Requirement” object is made equivalent to the [System Requirement Specification \(SyRS\)](#)⁴ as defined in ISO 29148 to permit the life cycle processes. Their basic attributes, described in [table 1](#), can be mapped one-to-one to our [requirement object](#) attributes .

¹ISO/IEC/IEEE 29148:2018, Systems and software engineering – Life cycle processes – Requirements engineering. <https://www.iso.org/standard/72089.html>

²Object Management Group (OMG), Requirements Interchange Format (ReqIF) Version 1.2. <https://www.omg.org/spec/ReqIF/1.2/>

³NIST (National Institute of Standards and Technology), Open Security Controls Assessment Language (OSCAL) Model Specifications. <https://pages.nist.gov/OSCAL/>

⁴ISO-29148 System Requirement Template: <https://www.reqview.com/doc/iso-iec-ieee-29148-templates/>

Attribute	Type	ISO 29148	Description
Id	String	ForeignID	A persistent unique identifier
Heading	String	Name	A short, human-readable title for the requirement.
Text	XHTML/ String	Text	The formal requirement statement
Type	Enum	Type	Categorization: Functional, Non-functional, Information, or Policy.
Priority	Enum	Priority	Stakeholder importance: Essential, Conditional, or Optional.
Rationale	XHTML/ String	Rationale	The underlying reason or business case for the requirement.
Source	String	Source	Originating stakeholder, document, or legal mandate.
Owner	String	Owner	The entity or WP responsible for the requirement's maintenance.
Verification Method	Enum	Verif. Method	Defined as: Inspection, Analysis, Demonstration, or Test.
Status	Enum	Workflow Metadata	The current lifecycle state (e.g., Draft, Approved, Baselined).

Table 1. Basic list of attributes of a System Requirement Specification object.

Requirement Quality Criteria

ISO 29148 (Clause 5.2) defines a set of characteristics that well-formed requirements should exhibit in order to support effective analysis, validation, and management. In EOSC-ENTRUST, these criteria are used to guide requirement screening, clarification, and traceability activities. Core characteristics of a good requirement are:

- **Necessary:** the requirement reflects a genuine stakeholder need or constraint.
- **Unambiguous:** the requirement has only one possible interpretation.
- **Complete:** the requirement includes sufficient information to be understood and assessed.
- **Consistent:** the requirement does not conflict with other requirements.
- **Singular:** the requirement expresses one need or constraint.
- **Feasible:** the requirement can be realistically implemented within given constraints.
- **Traceable:** the requirement can be traced to its source and related artefacts.
- **Verifiable:** there exists a means to determine whether the requirement has been satisfied.

4.2 Requirement Interchange Format (ReqIF)

The Requirement Interchange Format (ReqIF) is an open, XML-based standard developed by the Object Management Group (OMG) specifically designed to enable the loss-less exchange of requirements, metadata, and traceability links between heterogeneous software tools. In this RMP, ReqIF is utilized as reference for the “Requirement” object, which is equivalent in its core to the ReqIF `SpecObject` formal type and its associated `SpecRelation` class that enforces the requirements bidirectional traceability. [Appendix C: Reference Standards Mapping and Structures](#) includes a detailed view of these objects. This approach ensures versionable and structured requirement definitions, with explicit links between high-level stakeholder needs and low-level technical specifications.

This standardized schema can be processed by a wide array of industrial and open-source RE tooling, enabling stakeholders to import requirements baselines into their preferred local management environments without data degradation.

4.3. Open Security Controls Assessment Language (OSCAL)

The Open Security Controls Assessment Language (OSCAL) is a multi-layered set of formats expressed in XML, JSON, and YAML that provides a standardized, machine-readable way to represent, manage, and automate security control, system security plans, and assessment results. While ReqIF handles the requirements themselves, the “Evidence” and “Assessment” objects proposed in this RMP (see [7.1 Conceptual Model](#)) are conceptually aligned with the OSCAL framework. This RMP adopts the Requirement-Evidence-Assessment model that mirrors OSCAL philosophy by decoupling the requirement definition (i.e. controls) from its evidence-based traceability (implementation) and subsequent structured assessment results (Assessment Results⁵). The model specifically leverages the Assessment Results (AR) where evidence provided by a TRE or the federation is encapsulated in the observation and relevant-evidence structures. [Appendix C: Reference Standards Mapping and Structures](#) provides conceptual examples. The same principles apply when this RMP establishes the Evidence Quality Criteria (see [8.3 Evidence assessment](#)).

This approach enables the transition from manual, point-in-time audits to continuous monitoring and automated CaC (see maturity levels of [8.1 Traceability Model](#)).

5. Requirements Processing and Lifecycle Management

This section defines the requirements management lifecycle adopted in EOSC-ENTRUST. Given their Driver-derived origin, ENTRUST requirements do not uniformly meet all quality characteristics (see “Requirement Quality Criteria” at [4.1 ISO/IEC/IEEE 29148:2018](#)) at elicitation time. The present lifecycle introduces specific phases to progressively bridge the gap between “Stakeholder Needs” and “System Requirements.”

⁵OSCAL concept layers, <https://pages.nist.gov/OSCAL/learn/concepts/layer/>

The controlled lifecycle comprises two distinct but interconnected stages:

- **Stage I – Requirements Development and Baseline:** Stage I establishes the approved requirements baseline through five structured phases of requirements engineering activities.
- **Stage II – Requirements Maintenance (Phase 6):** Stage II governs the controlled modification and maintenance of that baseline in accordance with configuration management principles.

The transition between the two stages occurs upon formal baseline approval and repository registration. The following diagram summaries the whole lifecycle:

Figure 1. Requirements Management Lifecycle

The following subsections detail the six phases of the Requirements Lifecycle. Each phase is first framed in terms of its alignment with ISO 29148 and subsequently described in the specific context of EOSC-ENTRUST.

Phase 1 - Stakeholder Requirements Elicitation

In ISO 29148 terms (Clause 6 – Stakeholder Needs and Requirements Definition), the purpose of this phase is to identify and capture stakeholder needs, expectations, and constraints in a structured manner, without introducing implementation assumptions, architectural decisions, or design solutions.

In the context of EOSC-ENTRUST, this phase focuses on capturing requirements from a multi-stakeholder environment characterised by heterogeneous technical, organisational,

and regulatory contexts, while preserving the original intent and rationale of each requirement.

Stakeholder requirements are elicited primarily from the ENTRUST Drivers, with validation and feedback from ENTRUST TRE Providers and relevant Work Packages. Drivers represent complementary and representative use-cases for federated, multinational use of TRE environments across scientific domains and user communities. Their role is to articulate expectations, needs, and constraints that TREs must address in order to support real research practice.

The outcome of this phase is a consolidated set of stakeholder requirements reflecting an end-user and operational perspective, which serves as the input for subsequent analysis, clarification, and traceability activities.

Requirements Identification and documentation

Requirements are identified following a common methodological approach to ensure consistency across Drivers, while allowing for domain-specific expression. A design thinking-inspired process is used to structure elicitation, typically including:

- identification of the core problem addressed by the Driver,
- definition of relevant user roles,
- description of user journeys and interaction points,
- derivation of requirements from user needs and constraints.

This approach supports the identification of gaps, overlaps, and differing priorities across Drivers without prematurely constraining the solution space.

At this stage, requirements are not required to be fully testable, feasible, or implementation-ready, but they:

- are captured close to their original context (Driver, use-case, or scenario) to preserve intent,
- may vary in granularity, scope, and level of abstraction,
- may overlap or partially duplicate other requirements.

Requirements are meant to be documented in a structured and lightweight format (e.g. spreadsheets) suitable for further analysis and traceability in subsequent phases. In the context EOSC-ENTRUST, elicitation activities and resulting requirement inventories are documented in detail in project milestones MS7⁶ and MS8⁷. These milestones represent two iterative and progressive rounds of requirements collection and consolidation, each resulting in a published requirement inventory. The inventories are made publicly available as spreadsheets and constitute the input for subsequent lifecycle phases.

⁶EOSC-ENTRUST MS7 Initial Driver Requirements for TREs from the four Drivers. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17434188>

⁷EOSC-ENTRUST MS8 Revised Driver Requirements for TREs from the four Drivers report. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17152104>

Requirements Mapping to Existing Frameworks

The purpose of requirements mapping is to establish explicit relationships between elicited stakeholder requirements and existing frameworks, architectures or standards so that elicited requirements extend, refine, or contextualise existing requirements rather than duplicating them. As such, the process is not a compliance exercise but an analytical activity.

In EOSC-ENTRUST, each elicited requirement is explicitly mapped against:

- SATRE2⁸ (Standardised Architecture for Trusted Research Environments): by the identification of the SATRE capability or capability group most closely related to the requirement. SATRE2 serves as an initial reference model to categorise TRE capabilities and to provide a shared vocabulary for discussing TRE functionality.
- ENTRUST Blueprint⁹: by the identification of the architectural components able to allocate the elicited requirement. Where requirements cannot be meaningfully mapped to existing Blueprint components, this is recorded as a potential gap and used as structured feedback for Blueprint evolution.

Alignment and mapping information is maintained as requirement metadata and carried forward into subsequent lifecycle phases to support traceability, impact analysis, and sustainability.

Phase 2 - Requirements Analysis

In ISO 29148 terms (Clause 7 – Requirements Analysis Process), the purpose of this phase is to analyse elicited stakeholder requirements in order to improve their structure, clarity, consistency, and suitability for further processing, without introducing design or implementation decisions.

In EOSC-ENTRUST, requirements analysis addresses the inherent heterogeneity of Driver-derived requirements, which may differ in granularity, terminology, scope, and level of abstraction. This phase prepares requirements for traceability, validation, and baseline registration while preserving their original intent and contextual meaning.

Prioritisation and Impact Analysis

Prioritisation and impact analysis is performed to support comparison across requirements originating from different Drivers. A qualitative prioritisation approach (e.g. SWOT-based analysis) may be used to:

- identify strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and risks associated with requirements
- highlight requirements with broad impact, cross-cutting relevance, or high dependency potential

⁸A Standard Architecture for Trusted Research Environments (1.01). Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10053383>

⁹EOSC-ENTRUST D14.3 Year two version of EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint & Interoperability Framework. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18299343>

- expose tensions or trade-offs between requirements

Where Drivers provide prioritisation input, this information is consolidated to derive an indicative priority level (e.g. average or consensus-based), which is recorded as requirement metadata.

Clarification and Scoping Analysis

The analysis focuses on making stakeholder requirements understandable, bounded, and suitable for traceability and verifiability, while preserving their original intent. The analysis constitutes a first quality update and should be structured around a set of explicit focus areas described in [Table 2](#), each addressing a specific aspect of requirement clarity, scope, and traceability.

Analysis Focus	Description	Requirement Metadata
Clarity and Terminology Harmonisation	Requirements are reviewed to reduce ambiguity or inconsistent terminology. Where feasible, readability is improved but domain-specific terms are retained to preserve intent. Clarifications are recorded as requirement metadata	Clarification Notes
Overlap and Relationship Identification	Overlaps and relationships with other requirements are identified, preserving traceability to original sources.	relatedRequirements
Assumptions and Dependencies	Contextual, technical or organisational assumptions are explicitly recorded.	Clarification Notes
Scope Boundaries and Responsibility Domains	Clearly distinguish requirement responsibility scope: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - TRE-level - Federation-level, - External responsibilities 	Scope Attribution

Table 2. Clarification and scoping analysis: purpose and outcomes

Clarification and scoping analysis does not exclude requirements based on feasibility or maturity. Instead, limitations, dependencies, and uncertainties are recorded as structured metadata to support downstream verifiability analysis and evidence-based assessment.

Phase 3 - Requirements verification analysis

In alignment with ISO 29148 (Clause 6 and Clause 7), this phase addresses requirements quality evaluation and preparation for verification and validation. It assesses whether requirements are stated in a manner that enables objective verification and whether their satisfaction can, in principle, be demonstrated through evidence. Verification answers “are requirements suitable, testable, verifiable?”, while validation planning answers “how would

this be demonstrated?”. It is not required that all requirements immediately map to evidence; rather, the ability to do so is a quality criterion.

In the context of EOSC-ENTRUST, this phase was operationalised through a structured stakeholder workshop aimed at assessing the verifiability of elicited and analysed requirements and exploring how their adoption could be evidenced within TRE environments.

Verifiability screening

Following Phase 2, requirements were screened to assess their suitability for objective verification. The purpose of this screening was to evaluate whether a requirement could be demonstrated through observable and assessable evidence within the scope of TRE or federation responsibilities.

Requirements were classified as “Verifiable”, “Not Verifiable” or “Partially Verifiable” depending on potential linkage to evidence. “Not Verifiable” requirements were screened out for the following considerations:

- **Too abstract:** The requirement lacks measurable or observable characteristics and requires further refinement.
- **Out of scope:** The requirement addresses responsibilities outside the defined operational or governance boundary.
- **Externally dependent:** Demonstration of compliance depends on actors or systems not governed by the TRE or federation structure.

Where necessary, requirements classified as “Partially Verifiable” or “Not Verifiable” can be fed back to the Requirements Analysis phase.

Evidence-based verifiability test

The test consists of stakeholders performing an evidence elicitation exercise for requirements classified as “Verifiable” or “Partially Verifiable”. Each requirement is linked to a set of evidence suggestions or examples that could demonstrate requirement adoption. Evidence mapping is undergone as stated in section [8.1. Traceability Model](#), that proposes the use of a RATM as a tool to keep track of the suggested evidence.

This activity supports verification and validation planning, while providing examples of artefacts, documentation, processes, or system characteristics very valuable for identifying gaps and guiding development of the federated TREs.

Phase 4 - Requirements Stakeholder Validation

In ISO 29148 (Clause 6) terms, the purpose of this phase is to confirm that requirements accurately reflect stakeholder intent and are suitable for their intended use. Validation ensures that the documented requirements reflect a shared understanding among stakeholders and address the identified problem space.

In EOSC-ENTRUST, the process for reviewing and approval of finalized requirements is performed through reviews with TRE providers, Drivers, and relevant experts (e.g. Providers

meetings, Drivers feedback loops, workshop recap sessions). Validation focuses on shared understanding and interpretation, not on compliance assessment.

Phase 5 - Requirements Baseline Registration

In alignment with ISO 29148, this phase establishes the approved requirements baseline and places it under configuration control. Baseline ensures that requirements are uniquely identified, stable, and formally managed, thereby enabling traceability, change control, and auditability throughout subsequent lifecycle activities.

In EOSC-ENTRUST, baseline registration is performed once requirements have been uniquely identified, analysed, validated, and approved. All requirements are registered in a central Requirements Repository (see [9.2 Requirements Repository](#)), which serves as the authoritative and structured source of truth. The repository supports version control and provides associated human-readable representations (e.g. the Requirements Catalogue).

Registration includes the assignment of a unique and persistent identifier and the completion of formal metadata fields in accordance with the conceptual model described in section [7.1 Conceptual Model](#). Once registered, requirements become part of an official baseline and are subject to controlled change management.

The MS8 requirements set constitutes the Initial Requirements Baseline for EOSC-ENTRUST.

Phase 6 - Change Control and Maintenance

In alignment with ISO 29148, this phase addresses requirements management following baseline establishment. It ensures that approved requirements are maintained under configuration control and that any proposed modifications are systematically evaluated, approved, implemented, and traceable. This phase supports impact analysis, version control, and preservation of baseline integrity throughout the system life cycle.

In EOSC-ENTRUST, Phase 6 constitutes the operational governance process responsible for maintaining and evolving the established requirements baseline. Unlike the preceding phases, which focus on stakeholder-driven requirements development, this phase is managed by the designated TRE governance and change control structure.

Change Control and Maintenance ensures that registered requirements are maintained under controlled versioning, with traceability and governance oversight. This phase ensures that baselined requirements remain stable while still allowing structured adaptation to emerging technical, regulatory, and operational needs.

A recommended best-practice approach is the adoption of a Change Control Workflow, where requirements are treated as version-controlled digital artefacts. Git-based workflows provide a natural operationalization of this model, where:

- **Change Initiation**

Proposed changes are submitted and recorded as structural Change Requests (CR) (e.g., issues in a version-controlled platform). Contributors issue new CRs, providing

rationale, scope, and impact of the proposed change by following a standardised structure (see [Appendix B: Change Request Form template](#)).

- **Change Review and Approval**

Changes are evaluated before implementation by designated roles (see [6. Roles and Responsibilities](#)). “Requirements Reviewers” assess clarity, feasibility, and traceability implications, and “Requirements Owners” or “Change Control Authorities” approve or reject CRs. Only approved changes are integrated into the registered baseline through reviewed update mechanisms (e.g., pull requests in a version-controlled platform) by the “Requirements Maintainer”. The workflow ensures accountability of change decisions and auditability of modifications, while allowing for the enforcement of a standardized and controlled version tagging system to preserve baseline integrity.

- **Versioning and Baseline Integrity**

Approved changes result in an incremented version of the affected requirement(s), updated following agreed versioning rules public (e.g., [CONTRIBUTING.md](#)¹⁰, [CodeOfConduct.md](#)¹¹). Where changes affect multiple requirements or introduce structural changes, a new baseline version may be created. The Change Control Authority (see section [Governance Roles](#)), is responsible to issue new baselines. In Git-based implementations, they could correspond to tagged or released artifacts. A frozen baseline is suitable to be the object of point-in-time assessment processes (see [8.3 Evidence assessment](#)).

- **Change Logging and Traceability**

To support auditability and lifecycle traceability, each change should be uniquely identified, linked to affected requirements, and documented in a Change Log (e.g., [CHANGELOG.md](#)¹²) that captures audit information like the CR identifier, the approval date and/or the Reviewer. Previous versions remain accessible to preserve historical traceability.

All changes are recorded in the Requirements Repository (see [9.2 Requirements Repository](#)) to preserve traceability between baseline versions.

Phase 6 forms Stage II and operates as a continuous governance process. Thus it does not repeat the elicitation, analysis, or validation activities of Stage I. Its purpose is to ensure controlled evolution of the requirements set while safeguarding consistency, traceability, and auditability.

6. Roles and Responsibilities

This section defines the set of functional roles involved in supporting the operational needs of applying the full RMP end-to-end in practice, including the production, review, and maintenance of evidence artefacts. The roles are described in terms of responsibilities and

¹⁰CONTRIBUTING guidelines for EOSC-ENTRUST Requirements Repository,

https://github.com/inab/ENTRUST_TRE_Requirements_Repository/blob/main/CONTRIBUTING.md

¹¹Code of Conduct for EOSC-ENTRUST Requirements Repository,

https://github.com/inab/ENTRUST_TRE_Requirements_Repository/blob/main/CODE_OF_CONDUCT.md

¹²Changelog for EOSC-ENTRUST Requirements Repository,

https://github.com/inab/ENTRUST_TRE_Requirements_Repository/blob/main/CHANGELOG.md

lifecycle involvement rather than organisational positions or governance bodies to further ease alignment and consistency. Although existing roles are already conceptually consistent across existing TRE architectural standards (DARE UK FAB v2.2¹³, SATRE, etc), they only partially cover the range of roles typically required to support comprehensive requirements engineering activities. That’s why this RMP takes as reference a minimal and simplified set of actors aligned with ISO 29148. This standard defines requirements lifecycle processes and associated responsibilities, but does not prescribe specific role names. The roles defined in this RMP operationalise these responsibilities within the EOSC-ENTRUST context. The list of roles is meant to be minimal and realistic, assuming multiple roles may be fulfilled by the same actor depending on organisational size and maturity.

The natural linkage to actual actors highly depends on the specifics of the architecture or the governance model being applied. A typical or potential actor candidate is given in the table in the context of EOSC-ENTRUST. Most of the roles are expected to remain relevant beyond EOSC-ENTRUST, potentially under the OTPF.

Pre-registration Roles

These roles support stage I (phases 1-5) of the requirements management lifecycle. They support the requirements engineering activities prior to formal registration and baseline establishment.

Role	Primary Responsibility	Key Responsibilities	ISO 29148 Compliance	SATRE v1.1 Mapping	Lifecycle Steps	Candidate Actors
Requirements Contributor	Provision of requirements input and domain knowledge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Propose new requirements Provide context, rationale, and assumptions Explain stakeholder needs and constraints 	Stakeholder / Requirement Source	-	Elicitation, Analysis, Clarification	Drivers (<i>i.e.</i> Researcher), TRE providers
Requirements Reviewer	Assessment of requirement quality and readiness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assess clarity, scope and traceability Identify overlaps Identify and flag high-risk, unverifiable or infeasible requirements 	Requirements Reviewer / Risk-informed Validator	Quality Manager (<i>conceptual</i>)	Analysis, Screening, Validation	Cross-WP experts (technical / legal experts), designated reviewers

Table 3. List of roles involved in requirements elicitation and validation

¹³DARE UK Federated Architecture Blueprint (2.2). Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14192786>

Post-Registration Roles

These roles support stage II (phase 6) of the requirements management lifecycle. At this point, requirements are well-established and ready to be applied for demonstrating adoption. These roles not only support maintenance activities (phase 6), but also operational activities for demonstrating adoption of requirements (e.g. artefact collection and implementation of internal or external audits).

Role	Primary Responsibility	Key Responsibilities	ISO 29148 Compliance	SATRE v1.1 Mapping	Lifecycle Steps	Candidate Actors
Requirements Owner	Own requirement definition and scope	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Approve clarifications and assumptions • Decide on requirement changes 	Requirement Owner	Top Mngt. (governance)	Clarification, Registration, Change Control	TRE federation body, OTPF
Requirements Maintainer	Operational maintenance of requirements artefacts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintain Requirements Repository (Git) • Version and publish baselines • Ensure metadata completeness 	Information Mngt.		Registration, Maintenance	TRE federation body, OTPF
Evidence Producer	Production of concrete evidence artefacts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Produce and maintain evidence proving adoption • Document scope and context of evidence 	Contributor to Verification	Data Steward, Information Asset Owner	Implementation	See section 6.2 Candidate Actors Producing Evidences
Evidence Assessor	Review and validation of evidence against requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assess evidence relevance • Perform manual or automated checks • Record assessment outcomes 	Verification / Validation Authority	Auditor, Quality Manager (<i>conceptual</i>)	Review, Validation	TRE auditor, internal or external (e.g. TRE federation body)
Evidence Repository Maintainer	Management of evidence storage and access	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintain evidence repositories • Ensure proofs integrity, access control and retention 	Information Mngt.		Storage, Maintenance	TRE federation body or TRE operations

Table 4. List of roles involved in post-registration operational roles

Governance Roles

These roles support the decision-making, conflict resolution and external assurance interface activities. They support both State II activities and operational activities in the context of interfacing with external audit or certification bodies.

Role	Primary Responsibility	Key Responsibilities	ISO 29148 Compliance	SATRE v1.1 Mapping	Lifecycle Steps	Candidate Actors
Change Control Authority	Governance of requirement and evidence changes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Approve significant changes • Resolve conflicts and overlaps • Authorise baseline update 	Change Control Authority	Top Mngt.	Change Mngt.	OTPF
Audit Interface	Interface with external audit or certification bodies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prepare evidence packages • Support audits or assessments • Map artefacts to external criteria 	External Validation Interface	Auditor, Information Governance Manager	Audit, Assurance	TRE federation body

Table 5: List of governance roles involved

6.1 Role Responsibilities in Requirements Lifecycle

This RACI view (Responsible / Accountable / Consulted / Informed) summarises and clarifies responsibilities across the requirements and evidence lifecycle, without prescribing organisational structures.

- **R** = Responsible: performs the activity
- **A** = Accountable: has ownership and ultimate decision
- **C** = Consulted: provides input
- **I** = Informed: is kept aware

Lifecycle Activity	Req. Contrib.	Req. Revisor	Req. Owner	Req. Maint.	Evidence Producer	Evidence Reviewer	Repo. Maint.	Change Control Auth.	Audit Interf.
Req. elicitation	RA	C	I	I	–	–	–	–	–
Req. analysis & clarification	C	R	A	I	–	–	–	–	–
Screening & traceability	C	R	A	I	–	–	–	–	–
Req. registration & maintenance	I	C	A	R	–	–	–	C	–

Req. baselining & versioning	I	C	C	R	-	-	-	A	-
Change request evaluation	I	C	C	R	-	-	-	A	-
Evidence production	-	-	I	I	RA	C	-	-	-
Evidence storage & linking	-	-	I	C	C	-	RA	-	-
Evidence review & validation	-	-	I	I	C	RA	C	-	-
Consolidated assessment view	-	-	C	C	C	RA	C	-	I
Audit support	-	-	I	I	C	C	C	-	RA

Table 6: RACI view for the requirements management lifecycle

6.2 Candidate Actors Producing Evidences

Identifying actors or personas adopting the requirements lifecycle functional roles depends on the operationalization of the RMP and is not covered here, we are only giving candidate actors. Yet, it is worth achieving greater granularity for the “Evidence Producer” role, as the adoption of requirements within TREs is demonstrated through verifiable evidence artefacts produced by these actors. As such, these actors are responsible for governance, legal compliance, technical operations and data use within TREs. They are to be trusted and are important for the accountability and responsibilities in the verification process. For this reason it is important to scope responsibilities well. Moreover, we can assign typical actors more than candidate actors as TRE operational and governance actors are well defined in standardization frameworks like SATRE2.

The table below lists the primary evidence-producing actors, their functional responsibilities, the types of evidence they typically generate, and their conceptual alignment with SATRE v1.1 roles, where applicable, as they primarily focus on TRE operational and governance functions.

Actor	Responsibilities	Evidence Types	SATRE2 Mapping
TRE Manager	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintain data governance frameworks • Define data lifecycle and retention policies • Approve and document governance-level decisions • Validate compliance with DSAs/DUAs • Approve and document system or policy changes 	GOV, COMPL, DOC	Top Management / Information Governance Manager
Data Protection Officer (DPO)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Produce DPIAs • Provide GDPR compliance documentation • Define and approve security and privacy policies 	GOV, COMPL, DOC	Information Governance Manager
Data Access Officer (DAO)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Manage data access request workflows • Approve or document access decisions • Maintain eligibility and onboarding records 	GOV, COMPL, OPS	DAC / Governance Manager
Legal Officer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide signed DSAs/DUAs • Ensure contractual and regulatory compliance 	GOV, COMPL, DOC	~ Legal Counsel
Ethics Officer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide ethics approval letters • Ensure consent processes and documentation • Document DAC or ethics committee decisions 	GOV, COMPL, HEALTH	Ethics Committee / Governance
Technical Administrator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Produce vulnerability scan reports • Provide CI/CD logs and IaC artefacts • Export system configurations and platform settings • Generate encryption, network, backup, and restore evidence 	TECH, OPS, AUTO	Operator / Infrastructure Manager
TRE Operations Officer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide operational workflow logs • Document incidents and helpdesk records • Maintain SOPs, SLAs, monitoring and usage logs • Provide change control records 	TECH, OPS	Operator
Identity & Access Manager	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Manage authentication and authorisation workflows • Provide ACLs and identity metadata • Deliver access review and recertification logs 	TECH, OPS, COMPL	Identity and Access Management
Data Steward	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Define and document SDC rules • Describe sensitive data handling workflows • Ensure domain-specific safety controls 	HEALTH, COMPL, GOV	Data Steward
Output Checker (SDC Reviewer)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Apply SDC rules to outputs • Provide output checking logs • Document output release decisions 	HEALTH, OPS, TRAIN	Output Checker
Training Coordinator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide evidence of user and SDC training • Maintain attendance and compliance logs • Ensure security and safe research training 	TRAIN	Training Coordinator

Table 7: List of actors producing evidence

7. Data Model

7.1 Conceptual Model

The EOSC ENTRUST RMP is based on a minimal conceptual model designed to support traceability, validation, and long-term sustainability in a federated TRE context. As depicted in [Figure 2](#), the model focuses on three core objects (“[Requirement](#)”, “[Evidence](#)”, “[Assessment](#)”) and their relationships to enable a systematic RM approach.

Figure 2: Core data objects of the conceptual model and their relationships

This model intentionally diverges from the lifecycle logic commonly found in classical systems engineering. Traditional RM frameworks assumes a system being designed and built to satisfy predefined specifications, so typically it follow a progression such as:

Requirement → Design → Implementation → Test → Verification

By contrast, EOSC-ENTRUST operates in a federated governance context where TREs are heterogeneous, pre-existing, and independently operated. The RMP therefore adopts a governance- and assurance-oriented logic structured as:

Requirement → Evidence → Audit/Review Assessment

Rather than prescribing design or implementation steps, the RMP focuses on documenting how existing organisational and technical solutions demonstrate alignment with agreed requirements. With this aim, the conceptual model supports:

- structured traceability between requirements and demonstrable artefacts

- repeatable assessment cycles over time
- progressive maturity from manual documentation to automated validation
- long-term interoperability with emerging compliance or assurance frameworks

Core Objects

The core object concepts are aligned with established standards at a functional level (see [4. Standards Alignment](#)). “Requirements” are represented in a manner functionally equivalent to ReqIF for interchange and versioning. The “Evidence” and “Assessment” concepts draw conceptually from OSCAL terminology, particularly in their treatment of structured artefacts and evaluative records.

Figure illustrates the verification chain, where a single “Requirement” is demonstrated by multiple and ideally complementary pieces of “Evidence” across multiple dimensions (e.g., technical, operational, governmental). Each “Evidence” is subject to a point-in-time assessment process, which records the Assessor's validation results.

Figure 3: UML diagram of the Data Model

. The “Requirement” object is intentionally decoupled from “Evidence” and “Assessment” objects and their relationships are explicitly recorded for traceability (see section [8.1 Traceability Model](#)). This conceptual model is intentionally minimal to ensure usability beyond the project and compatibility with open standards such as ReqIF and OSCAL concepts. The model supports methodological analysis and transparency without introducing mandatory tooling or governance dependencies. Following subsections include a full description of each the data model attributes.

7.2 Requirement Formal Definition

This section defines the formal structure of a *managed requirement*, a requirement that has passed initial analysis and is suitable for registration and baseline control. To ensure interoperability and reuse, the “Requirement” object is defined as functionally equivalent to a ReqIF “SpecObject”, with a controlled set of ISO compliant attributes that would allow easy mapping to other RM frameworks.

Each “Requirement” object shall include the attributes listed below. The full structure is described using data schemas (see [9.1 Data model JSON schemas](#)), that technically enforce and validate the structure.

Requirement Attribute	Type	Card.	Description	Controlled Vocabulary / Ref. Object
Requirement ID	String	1..1	Unique and persistent identifier assigned at registration time. Must remain stable across versions.	
Title	String	1..1	Short, human-readable name of the requirement.	
Description	Text	1..1	Normative requirement statement expressed in clear, precise, and testable language where possible.	
Version	String	1..1	Version identifier managed through controlled versioning (e.g., Git-based control).	
Baseline ID	String	0..1	Identifier or tag of the frozen set of requirements considered to be a baseline. Once issued, the requirement is ready for evidence linkage and assessment.	
Status	Enum	1..1	Current lifecycle state of the requirement.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Draft</i>: Under development or refinement, not yet validated • <i>Reviewed</i>: Analysed and validated by stakeholders • <i>Baselined</i>: Formally approved and registered. • <i>Deprecated</i>: No longer active, retained for historical traceability
Priority	Int	1..1	Relative importance or criticality of the requirement.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0: Informational, desirable but not critical • 1: Low, minor impact if not satisfied • 2: Medium, important for operational/ governance integrity. • 3: High, critical for trust, security, legal, or federation viability.
Source	String	1..1	Originating stakeholder, Driver, framework, or artefact from which the requirement derives.	
Rationale	Text	0..1	Explanation of purpose, justification, or problem addressed by the requirement.	

Category	Enum	0..1	High-level thematic classification.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Governance, Legal and Trust • Security, AAI and Output Control • Data Lifecycle, Quality and FAIRness • Federation, Usability and Advanced Capabilities 								
Clarification Notes	Text	0..n	Interpretative notes added during analysis to clarify scope without altering the normative statement.									
Scope Attribution	Enum	1..1	Responsibility boundary indicating where the requirement applies.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TRE-level: applies to individual TRE environments • Federation-level: applies to cross-TRE coordination or governance structures • External actor: applies to entities interacting with the federation but not operating a TRE (e.g., data holders) 								
Framework Mappings	Obj	0..n	References to related elements in recognised frameworks or models.	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Attribute</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>frameworkId</td> <td>Identifier (e.g. "SATRE")</td> </tr> <tr> <td>value</td> <td>Framework specific ref.</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Attribute	Description	frameworkId	Identifier (e.g. "SATRE")	value	Framework specific ref.		
Attribute	Description											
frameworkId	Identifier (e.g. "SATRE")											
value	Framework specific ref.											
Related Requirements	Obj	0..n	Explicit relationships to other requirements.	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Attribute</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Requirement ID</td> <td>Id. of the referenced Requirement</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Baseline ID</td> <td>Id. of the Requirement baseline</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Relation</td> <td> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Refines • Depends on • Overlaps with </td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Attribute	Description	Requirement ID	Id. of the referenced Requirement	Baseline ID	Id. of the Requirement baseline	Relation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Refines • Depends on • Overlaps with
Attribute	Description											
Requirement ID	Id. of the referenced Requirement											
Baseline ID	Id. of the Requirement baseline											
Relation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Refines • Depends on • Overlaps with 											

Table 8: Simplified attribute list of the "Requirement" data object

7.3 Evidence Formal Definition

This section defines the formal structure of an “Evidence” object . It is designed to conceptually match assessment activities as defined in the NIST OSCAL (see [4.3. Open Security Controls Assessment Language \(OSCAL\)](#)).

This RMP proposes the following list of “Evidence” reference attributes. The full structure is described using data schemas (see [9.1 Data model JSON schemas](#)), that technically enforce and validate the structure. Notice that depending on the particular assessment context and the traceability maturity level implemented, new attributes might be added, or the cardinality of the existing attributes adjusted.

Evidence Attribute	Type	Card.	Description	Controlled Vocabulary / Ref. Object
Evidence ID	string	1..1	Unique, persistent identifier assigned at registration.	
Title	string	1..1	Short descriptive label identifying the artefact.	
Description	string	0..1	Brief explanation of what the evidence demonstrates and its relation to the supported Requirement(s).	
Version	String	1..1	Version identifier of the object. Updated according to an agreed policy.	
Location URI	uri	1..1	Persistent URI (e.g. PURL, DOI) or repository reference where the evidence artefact is stored.	
Checksum	string	1..1	Cryptographic hash ensuring artefact integrity.	
Checksum Algorithm	string	1..1	Algorithm used to compute the checksum hash	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SHA-256 • SHA-512 • BLAKE2 • Other (specified in notes)
Collected Date	datetime	1..1	Date and time when the artefact was originally produced.	
Timestamp	datetime	1..1	Date and time when the evidence was registered in the repository.	

Signed	boolean	0..1	Indicates whether the artefact includes a digital signature or trusted attestation.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>true</i> • <i>false</i>
Media Type	string	0..1	MIME type of the artefact (e.g. application/pdf, application/json)	
Evidence Type	enum	1..1	Categorical classification supporting coverage analysis and reporting.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>GOV</i>: Governance or policy artefact defining organisational framework. • <i>TECH</i>: Technical configuration or system artefact demonstrating implemented controls. • <i>COMPL</i>: Legal or regulatory compliance artefact • <i>TRAIN</i>: Training or awareness artefact confirming competence. • <i>OPS</i>: Operational process record demonstrating monitoring or execution. • <i>DOC</i>: Documentation supporting transparency. • <i>HEALTH</i>: Domain-specific ethical or health governance artefact. • <i>AUTO</i>: Machine-generated artefact supporting automated compliance validation.
Evidence Maturity	enum	1..1	Level of formalisation and enforcement strength of the artefact.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Policy</i>: document defining expectations without direct enforcement. • <i>Process</i>: defined repeatable procedure implementing policy. • <i>Technical-control</i>: implemented technical mechanism. • <i>Automated-Control</i>: continuously operating or machine-verified automated control.
Responsible Actor	enum	1..1	Role responsible for producing, maintaining, or signing the evidence.	See Section 6.2 Candidate Actors Producing Evidences
Evidence Producer System	string	0..1	If applicable (depending on Evidence Maturity), system or pipelines ID producing the Evidence	

Evidence Scope Type	enum	1..1	High-level classification of the system, dataset, or component covered by the evidence artefact.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>full-TRE</i>: covers entire TRE implementation • <i>system-component</i>: covers a specific technical subsystem • <i>service</i>: covers a functional exposed capability • <i>dataset</i>: covers a specific dataset • <i>federation-layer</i>: covers cross-TRE federation layer • <i>external-entity</i> 						
Evidence Scope ID	string	0..1	Specific name or ID of the system, dataset, or component covered							
Architecture Specific	boolean	0..1	Indicates whether the evidence depends on a specific technical architecture or implementation.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • true • false 						
Expected Assessment Method	enum	0..1	Expected or foreseen method for reviewing the evidence during the assessment process.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Examine</i>: human examination of artefact or documentation • <i>Test</i>: tool-based or script-based validation • <i>Automated-test</i>: automatic tool-based validation or CI/CD validation • Interview: discussion with responsible actors • <i>Other</i>: Alternative method specified in notes 						
Related Requirements	Obj	1..*	Reference(s) to Requirement object(s) supported by this evidence.	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Attribute</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Requirement ID</td> <td>Id. of the referenced Requirement</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Baseline ID</td> <td>Id. of the Requirement baseline</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Attribute	Description	Requirement ID	Id. of the referenced Requirement	Baseline ID	Id. of the Requirement baseline
				Attribute	Description					
				Requirement ID	Id. of the referenced Requirement					
Baseline ID	Id. of the Requirement baseline									
Notes	string	0..1	Additional contextual information or dependencies.							

Table 9: Simplified attribute list of the “Evidence” data object

7.4 Assessment Formal Definition

This section defines the formal structure and role of an “Assessment” object. Assessment objects capture the outcome of reviewing evidence in relation to one or more requirements.

Assessment Attribute	Type	Card.	Description	Controlled Vocabulary / Reference						
Assessment ID	string	1..1	Unique, persistent identifier assigned at registration. Immutable after creation.							
Version	string	1..1	Version identifier of the assessment record to support change tracking.							
Assessment Date	datetime	1..1	Date and time on which the assessment was performed.							
Related Evidence	Object	1..*	Reference(s) to Evidence object(s) reviewed during assessment.	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Attribute</th> <th>Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Evidence ID</td> <td>Id. of the referenced Evidence</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Version</td> <td>Evidence Version</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Attribute	Description	Evidence ID	Id. of the referenced Evidence	Version	Evidence Version
Attribute	Description									
Evidence ID	Id. of the referenced Evidence									
Version	Evidence Version									
Assessment Method	enum	1..1	Method used to perform the assessment.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Examine</i>: human examination of artefact or documentation • <i>Test</i>: tool-based or script-based validation • <i>Automated-test</i>: automatic tool-based validation or CI/CD validation • <i>Interview</i>: discussion with responsible actors • <i>Other</i>: Alternative method specified in <i>notes</i> 						
Assessor Actor	enum	1..1	Actor taking role of Evidence Assessor (see 8.3 Evidence assessment).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Internal-reviewer</i>: Assessment performed within the TRE • <i>Federation-reviewer</i>: Assessment performed at federation level • <i>Peer-reviewer</i>: Assessment performed by another TRE within federation • <i>External-auditor</i>: Independent third-party assessor 						

				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Other</i>: Alternatives specified in Notes
Outcome	enum	1..1	Result of the assessment expressed using controlled vocabulary.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Acceptable</i>: the evidence is sufficient, relevant, and verifiable to demonstrate adoption. ● <i>Needs-clarification</i>: evidence is relevant but lacks sufficient context, scope, or explanation. Additional clarification required. ● <i>Needs-improvement</i>: Evidence partially demonstrates adoption but shows gaps or weaknesses preventing full validation. ● <i>Insufficient</i>: Evidence does not adequately demonstrate adoption. ● <i>Not-assessed</i>: The requirement or evidence has not yet been assessed.
Notes	string	0..1	Qualitative observations, limitations, assumptions, or contextual factors influencing the outcome.	
Follow Up Actions	xhtml	0..1	Identified actions or recommendations resulting from the assessment (e.g. clarification needed, additional evidence required).	

Table 10: Simplified attribute list of the “Assessment” data object

8. Requirements Traceability and Adoption Analysis

Requirements management does not end with baseline registration. To ensure that requirements remain meaningful and actionable, a structured mechanism is required to trace their implementation across heterogeneous TREs. This section defines the methodological framework used to analyse and document how requirements may be adopted and demonstrated through verifiable artefacts (*ie.* Evidence).

In the current context of EOSC-ENTRUST, the objective is not to impose compliance or implementation choices rather, to provide a transparent, structured, and reproducible approach to link requirements to supporting evidence, and eventually, evaluate them. At the current stage traceability activities are event-driven (*ie.* project review milestone or audits preparation) and there is no requirement for continuous monitoring mechanisms. Assessments are performed at defined review points (*e.g.*, project milestones, stakeholder

reviews, preparatory audit exercises). This ensures sustainability and compatibility with diverse TRE maturity levels, while establishing a foundation for future certification and audit frameworks.

8.1 Traceability Model

This phase is based on formally defined object types of the Data Model: Requirement, Evidence and Assessment (see [7. Data Model](#)). Traceability is achieved through explicit, version-controlled relationships between these objects. A Requirement may be demonstrated by multiple Evidence objects. An Evidence object may contribute to the assessment of multiple Requirements. An Assessment evaluates the adequacy of Evidence in relation to a defined Requirement and produces a documented outcome. This structured linkage enables transparency, reproducibility and adoption comparability across TREs.

The Traceability Model may be implemented differently depending on organisational maturity. As such, it is designed as an incremental maturity framework that allows TREs and federations to adopt structured traceability proportionally to their technical or governance capabilities.

Figure 3: Traceability maturity ladder (Level 0–3)

Level 0 – Informal Traceability

At Level 0, “Requirements” may be documented and “Evidence” may exist within organisational processes, but the relationships between them are implicit and not formally recorded. Assessments, if conducted, are narrative and undocumented or dispersed across informal artefacts. There is no structured repository linkage, no controlled vocabulary, and no reproducible analytical model. This level reflects an initial or exploratory state and does not provide systematic transparency or comparability across TREs.

Level 1 – Structured Traceability Matrix

Level 1, establishes structured traceability through explicit object definition and relationship documentation. Requirements, Evidence, and Assessments are recorded as structured objects using defined metadata fields and controlled vocabularies (see [7. Data Model](#)). Their relationships are documented in a Requirement Adoption Traceability Matrix (RATM), implemented as a structured, human-readable artefact such as a spreadsheet or tabular file with predefined fields (see exemplary template at [9.5 RATM template](#)).

Evidence artefacts are stored in a controlled Evidence Repository that ensures version control, consistent referencing, and stable identifiers. Evidence is produced as part of normal governance, operational, or technical processes. Trust in the roles producing evidence constitutes a foundational assumption at this level.

Assessment activities are manual and event-driven. They rely primarily on examination methods and produce documented outcomes using controlled vocabulary. It enables cross-TRE comparison and structured reporting. Assessments are point-in-time and contextual. No continuous monitoring or automated enforcement mechanisms are required.

Level 1 is intentionally low-overhead and sustainable. It does not require dedicated compliance platforms or continuous review cycles. At the same time, it establishes structural compatibility with audit preparation and future automation frameworks. It constitutes the baseline operational model of this RMP.

Level 2 – Structured Machine-Readable Traceability

Level 2 extends Level 1 by formalising Requirements, Evidence metadata, and Assessment records in machine-readable formats and managing them through dedicated repositories or requirements management tools, rather than solely in spreadsheets. Suitable implementations may include tools such as Git-based repositories storing structured JSON or YAML objects for Requirements, Evidence, and Assessment records, ReqIF-compatible tools (e.g. ReqIF Studio¹⁴, Eclipse RMF¹⁵, IBM DOORS¹⁶) or ad-hoc designed structured databases with interoperable objects.

Persistent identifiers are systematically applied and traceability relationships are stored as structured links rather than implicit matrix references. Mapping to external frameworks (e.g., SATRE, ENTRUST Blueprint) becomes machine-readable. Although not automatic, assessment activities might be systematically applied and version-controlled updates .

Thanks to the improved supporting infrastructure and tooling, Level 2 improves interoperability, scalability, and audit-readiness, while automation of evidence collection is not yet required.

Level 3 – Automated / Compliance-as-Code Traceability

Level 3 represents full integration with Compliance-as-Code methodologies and automated pipelines producing evidence. Requirements are expressed as Controls catalogues aligned

¹⁴ReqIF Studio, <https://www.reqif.academy/software/reqif-studio/>

¹⁵Eclipse Requirements Management Framework, <https://eclipse.dev/rmf/>

¹⁶IBM Engineering Requirements Management DOORS.

<https://www.ibm.com/products/requirements-management>

with recognised standards (*i.e.* OSCAL-based representations). The actual implementations and system components being evaluated are described in machine-readable terms so that evidence collection can be automated.

At this level, requirements repositories are integrated with infrastructure-as-code (IaC) and security tooling. Continuous validation checks may be embedded into CI/CD pipelines. Evidence artefacts such as configuration states, logs, and scan outputs are programmatically generated. Artefacts such as Assessment Reports or Plans of Action can also be automatically created in standardised formats. Compliance status may be evaluated continuously rather than solely at discrete review points.

Level 3 significantly reduces manual audit preparation effort and increases transparency and reliability. However, it requires advanced technical maturity, strong governance commitment, and well structured federated infrastructures.

8.2 Evidence Identification and Registration

Evidence production refers to the identification and maintenance of artefacts that may demonstrate the adoption of one or more requirements. These artifacts may correspond to a high variety of documents, for example:

- policies and governance documents;
- procedures and operational records
- technical configurations or system outputs;
- automated scan results or logs;
- training records or certifications.

To reduce overhead, evidence artefacts are expected to be produced as part of normal governance, legal, technical, or operational activities and remain under the control of the responsible role (see [6.2 Candidate Actors Producing Evidences](#)). These actors are the ones responsible to register them in a controlled Evidence Repository (see [9.4 Evidence Repository](#)) ensuring version control, stable referencing and integrity. Repository's access management should carefully consider the confidentiality level associated with each artefact.

Evidence elicitation and linkage to requirements shall be built on top of a stable and consistent collection of requirements clearly defined and unalterable: a baseline. As such, retrospective inspections are permitted. Moreover, each requirement is expected to be supported by one or more evidence. Ideally, adoption should be proved covering all requirements' dimensions, including governance, technical implementation and operability (see existing [Evidence Types](#)).

The whole process is to be recorded using traceability tools that systematically record and maintain "Evidence" metadata as defined in [7.3 Evidence Formal Definition](#). Although specific tools and infrastructure depend on the traceability maturity model, explicit reference to the location of the actual evidence artifact is expected.

8.3 Evidence assessment

Evidence assessment determines whether registered artefacts can sufficiently demonstrate the adoption of a requirement. Assessment activities are recorded as structured Assessment objects (see [7. Data Model](#)), that include references to the evaluated Requirement, the supporting Evidence, applied criteria, and the resulting assessment outcome (see [Outcome](#) controlled vocabulary). Depending on the assessment context, activities might be framed as:

- Self-assessment performed within the TRE
- Assessment performed at federation level, where assessor roles is taken by
 - A federation or community representative
 - A peer-reviewer from another TRE within federation
- Preparatory analysis for future audits or certification schemes carried out by an independent third-party assessor.

At Level 1, Evidence is predominantly examination-based while at higher maturity levels, evidence increasingly aligns with OSCAL-compliant structured artefacts enabling automated validation and reproducibility.

8.3.1 Evidence Quality Criteria

Following the verifiability principle of ISO 29148 and the machine-readable specifications of OSCAL, evidence supporting requirement adoption must enable independent reviewers—or automated systems—to determine the compliance status with high confidence. As such, evidence must satisfy the following criteria:

- **Authenticity and Provenance:** Evidence must have a verifiable origin. It must identify the specific TRE system, service, or actor responsible for the artifact (OSCAL [origin](#) and [actor](#) attributes). System-generated evidence (SGE) is preferred over narrative descriptions.
- **Technical Traceability:** Evidence must be explicitly linked to a requirement via a unique identifier. This ensures a verifiable audit trail between the observation and the specific requirement (OSCAL [relevant-evidence](#)).
- **Integrity and Non-Repudiation:** Evidence must be protected against tampering. For high-maturity assessments, objects should include a cryptographic hash (e.g., SHA-256) to ensure the artifact remains unchanged since its generation.
- **Machine-Readability:** Evidence should be structured to support automated processing. Formats such as JSON/CSV exports, signed logs, or configuration snapshots are prioritized to facilitate CaC across the federation.
- **Temporal Validity:** Evidence must include a mandatory timestamp. Assessment results are only considered "active" within a defined validity window, after which a new observation is required to maintain the verified status.

8.3.2 Evidence assessment criteria

Evidence is assessed using a common set of validation criteria to ensure consistent interpretation across evidence types (governance, technical, operational, automated) and

across TREs in federated contexts. As such, evidence is evaluated against the following criteria:

- **Authenticity:** Evidence must originate from a legitimate, trusted source and be attributable to the responsible actor or system. Where possible, artifacts should include provenance metadata or a signature (e.g., identifying the TRE administrator, DPO, security officer, or a trusted automated pipeline such as compliance tooling outputs).
- **Freshness:** Evidence must be sufficiently current to support a valid assessment. Freshness expectations depend on evidence type: policies should typically be within a defined review cycle (e.g., 12–24 months), technical scans within an operationally meaningful window (e.g., 3–6 months), logs must cover the assessment period under review, and backup evidence should demonstrate recent restore testing (e.g., within 12 months).
- **Completeness:** Evidence must cover the full scope of the requirement being assessed. This includes ensuring mandatory fields are populated (e.g., scope, actors, controls), and that the artifact reflects the complete system, process, or set of endpoints/services relevant to the requirement (rather than a partial view). For governance evidence, the scope should explicitly include the relevant data types (e.g., health, genomic, clinical) where applicable.
- **Integrity:** Evidence must be protected against unauthorised modification. Integrity mechanisms may include cryptographic checksums or signatures, controlled storage in an Evidence Repository (e.g., access-controlled document store or versioned repository such as Git LFS), and preference for system-produced outputs (e.g., logs/config exports) over screenshots unless screenshots are justified and appropriately annotated.
- **Relevance:** Evidence must directly support the specific requirement under assessment. Artifacts should demonstrate adoption of the requirement itself (not adjacent or generic practices), and must correspond to the correct system, service, and data context (i.e., not evidence from a different environment, system, or data type).
- **Verifiability:** Evidence must be independently reviewable by assessors (and, where applicable, by automated checks). Artifacts should reflect real implemented configuration or operational state rather than aspirational statements; automated outputs are preferred when feasible, and supporting details such as timestamps and metadata should enable reviewers to validate that the control is actually in effect. Screenshots may be used only when they include sufficient contextual metadata to support independent verification.

9. Supporting artefacts

The requirements engineering activities described in this RMP are intended to be supported by a set of structured artefacts that enable storage, validation and traceability of requirements and their associated evidence or assessment actions. This section defines the minimal functional expectations and reference implementations for these artefacts but does not mandate specific tooling as the degree of formalisation and tooling adopted may vary depending on the [8.1 Traceability Model](#). At lower maturity levels, artefacts may be maintained using lightweight documentation and manual linkage. Higher maturity levels

progressively require structured, machine-readable representations, formalised repositories, and automated validation or reporting mechanisms. Tooling choices should therefore be proportionate to the intended traceability maturity and governance objectives.

9.1 Data model JSON schemas

To formalise the data model defined in [Section 7](#), machine-readable JSON Schemas are provided for the Requirement and Evidence objects:

Requirement	https://github.com/inab/ENTRUST_TRE_Requirements_Repository/blob/main/schemas/requirement.schema.json
Evidence	https://github.com/inab/ENTRUST_TRE_Requirements_Repository/blob/main/schemas/evidence.schema.json

Table 11: JSON schemas for “Requirement” and “Evidence” data objects

The schemas support structural validation of “Requirement” and “Evidence” prior to registration and interoperability with external tooling. The schemas are informative and non-mandatory and alternatively, other structured representations (e.g., YAML, XML, ReqIF) may be adopted.

9.2 Requirements Repository

A Requirements Repository is recommended as the authoritative, version-controlled collection of registered requirement artefacts and their associated metadata. This repository constitutes the single source of truth for baselined requirements. The repository should support:

- **Discrete requirements artefacts:** each requirement maintained as a discrete artefact (e.g., one file per requirement with a unique identifier).
- **Structured representations:** requirements captured in structured, machine-readable formats (e.g., JSON, YAML, XML) to enable schema validation, interoperability, and automated processing.
- **Controlled versioning and baselining:** version control for all artefacts to preserve baselines, provide audit trails, and enable historical reconstruction.
- **Change governance and lifecycle management:** defined processes for proposing, reviewing, approving, and retiring requirements, including ownership and status tracking.
- **Traceability support:** maintain links between requirements and related artefacts (e.g. evidence, assessment results), including forward and backward trace.

Depending on the [8.1 Traceability Model](#) adopted, repository implementations may range from lightweight, structured DevOps platforms to dedicated RE systems. Environments such as Jira¹⁷, Azure DevOps¹⁸ or Git-based repositories with issue-based change control workflows can provide sufficient support for discrete requirement artefacts. Classical RM

¹⁷ Jira (Atlassian), <https://atlassian.com/software/jira>

¹⁸ Azure DevOps (Microsoft) <https://azure.microsoft.com/en-us/products/devops>

tools like IBM DOORS¹⁹, Siemens Polarion ALM²⁰, or Jira with plugins like Structure²¹ or Xray²² provide more advanced governance capabilities, although they may be too rigid to fit the assessment-based conceptual model of this RMP.

An exemplary Git-based repository has been developed to register EOSC-ENTRUST requirements derived from MS8.

EOSC-ENTRUST Requirement Repository	https://github.com/inab/ENTRUST_TRE_Requirements_Repository
-------------------------------------	---

Table 12: EOSC-ENTRUST Requirements Repository Access

9.3 Requirements Catalogue

A Requirements Catalogue may be published as a curated and structured presentation of a baselined set of requirements derived from the authoritative Requirements Repository. The catalogue provides a consolidated, human-readable view of registered requirements for dissemination, stakeholder consultation, or reference purposes.

Catalogues may be provided in document form (e.g., PDF, spreadsheet) online (e.g., web portals) or using structured interchange formats (e.g., ReqIF), and should they remain traceable to the originating repository baseline.

Derived from EOSC-ENTRUST Requirement Repository and deployed as Github Pages, an exemplary and simple online Catalogue is made accessible:

EOSC-ENTRUST Requirement Catalogue	https://inab.github.io/ENTRUST_TRE_Requirements_Repository/docs/
------------------------------------	---

Table 13: EOSC-ENTRUST Requirements Catalogue Access

9.4 Evidence Repository

An Evidence Repository is recommended as custodian of the controlled and versioned collection of evidence artefacts and associated metadata. The repository ensures that evidence (i.e. files) remains accessible, reviewable, and traceable over time, enabling traceability, integrity verification, and reproducibility of assessment outcomes.

At minimum, the Evidence Repository shall support:

- **Evidence Storage:** hosting of the actual physical evidence (e.g., documents, images, logs, reports, agreements) that demonstrated adoption.
- **Structured Metadata:** to enable targeted updates, review, and trace linking

¹⁹ IBM DOORS Next, <https://www.ibm.com/products/engineering-requirements-management>

²⁰ Siemens Polarion ALM, <https://polarion.plm.automation.siemens.com>

²¹ Structure Jira plugin, <https://tempo.io/structure>

²² Xray Jira plugin, <https://www.getxray.app>

- **Integrity control:** mechanisms to preserve and verify evidence integrity (e.g., recorded checksums, timestamps and collection date-time references) to support auditability and reproducibility.
- **Trace linkage:** evidence artefacts linkable to the requirements they support and referenceable by assessment records to demonstrate coverage and decision rationale.

The Evidence Repository may be logically or physically separated from the Requirements and Assessment Repositories, or co-located where governance arrangements permit. The specific software solution adopted shall ensure versioning, traceability, integrity preservation, and reproducibility consistent with the adopted traceability maturity level. General-purpose document management platforms, when properly configured with version control and metadata discipline, may fulfil repository functions (e.g., Microsoft SharePoint²³, Nextcloud²⁴, Dataverse²⁵). Governance, Risk and Compliance (GRC) platforms provide integrated workflow and assessment support (e.g., RSA Archer²⁶, ServiceNow GRC²⁷). A Git-based repository represents a lightweight and transparent implementation approach.

9.5 Assessment Repository

The Assessment Repository is the controlled collection of Assessment artefacts documenting the evaluation of Evidence against defined Requirements at a specific point in time. It ensures that assessment outcomes are traceable, versioned, and reproducible across assessment cycles. Additionally, the repository shall support generation of structured, audit-ready reports and enable reconstruction of decisions taken.

The repository does not require a dedicated platform and it may be implemented as a distinct or embedded collection of metadata within the RM infrastructure. Implementations may range from structured tabular records (lower maturity levels) to machine-readable assessment artefacts enabling automated validation and alignment analysis (higher maturity levels).

9.6 Requirement Adoption Traceability Matrix (RATM) template

The Requirement Adoption Traceability Matrix (RATM) is a supporting operational artefact aligned with the RMP conceptual model. It provides a consolidated, row-based view of evidence adoption and validation status, while artefacts remain in the controlled Requirements, Evidence, and Assessment repositories.

Each row in the RATM represents a single Evidence item and integrates attributes from the three core object domains:

- **Requirement-related columns:** Requirement ID, title/statement, category/domain, baseline reference.

²³ SharePoint, <https://www.microsoft.com/sharepoint>

²⁴ Nextcloud, <https://nextcloud.com/>

²⁵ Dataverse, <https://dataverse.org/>

²⁶ Archer, <https://www.archerirm.com/>

²⁷ ServiceNow GRC, <https://www.servicenow.com/products/grc.html>

- **Evidence-related columns:** Evidence title, description, maturity/status, location URI (repository reference), type, expected assessment method, responsible role. etc. (see [7.3 Evidence Formal Definition](#))
- **Assessment-related columns:** Assessor actor, assessment date/cycle, outcome, brief decision notes (see [7.4 Assessment Formal Definition](#)).

RATM is meant to support low maturity level traceability models, where it can act as a primary instrument for coverage monitoring, coordination of evidence recollection and tracking across assessment cycles. At higher maturity levels traceability is enforced through machine-readable objects and automated validation.

A RATM template has been developed as reference, and it is accessible at:

RATM template	https://github.com/inab/ENTRUST_TRE_Requirements_Repository/tree/main/templates
---------------	---

Table 14: EOSC-ENTRUST RATM template

10. Sustainability and Post-Project Use

The sustainability of the EOSC-ENTRUST RMP is based on the strategic decoupling of methodology from implementation. While aligning with international standards, the project delivers a methodological tool specially designed for managing evolving requirements from heterogeneous federations of varying degrees of maturity that remains agnostic to the underlying technical stack. This approach minimizes project-specific dependencies and enhances the requirements baseline remains a reusable and extensible asset for the European research community.

Governance is designed around functional roles rather than specific actors to facilitate the transfer of ownership. The OTPF is a potential candidate for post-project stewardship, providing a stable environment for the long-term maintenance of the requirements baseline with minimal administrative overhead. This role-based transition ensures that the methodology survives the project's funded lifespan.

Post-project, the RMP serves as a standardized reference methodology and a shared data model for the TRE federation. It provides the technical foundation for future Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and formal certification discussions. By establishing a unified vocabulary for Requirement, Evidence, and Assessment objects, the RMP enables the professionalization of TRE compliance processes across Europe, fostering long-term trust and interoperability.

Appendix A: Glossary

- **Assessment (Requirements Assessment):** a point-in-time evaluation activity that determines the extent to which a requirement is addressed, based on the validation

of one or more evidence artifacts against a set of validation criteria. In EOSC-ENTRUST, assessments are triggered by reviews or audits events and result in a qualitative assessment outcome using a controlled vocabulary.

- **Baseline (Requirements Baseline):** a versioned, formally registered set of managed requirements that has been reviewed and approved for use as a stable reference. Once baselined, requirements are subject to controlled change management.
- **Change Control:** a controlled process for proposing, reviewing, approving, and versioning changes to baselined requirements. In EOSC-ENTRUST, change control is implemented through version-controlled repositories and documented review workflows.
- **Evidence (Adoption Evidence):** a verifiable artefact demonstrating how a requirement is addressed in practice. Evidence may include policies, procedures, configurations, system outputs, logs, or automated assessment reports, and is produced by responsible actors and linked to one or more requirements.
- **Managed Requirement:** A requirement that has undergone analysis, clarification, scoping, and formal registration according to an agreed requirements management process. Managed requirements include structured metadata and are subject to version control and change management.
- **Requirement:** A statement that identifies a capability, constraint, or condition that must be met to address a stakeholder need. See also “Managed Requirement” and “Stakeholder Requirement”.
- **Requirement Lifecycle:** the defined sequence of phases through which requirements progress, from elicitation to baseline registration and maintenance, including analysis, verification, validation, and change control. The lifecycle is independent of implementation and supports consistent handling of requirements over time.
- **Requirements Management Plan (RMP):** a document defining the methodology, processes, roles, artefacts, and data models used to manage requirements throughout their lifecycle. An RMP provides a structured basis for traceability, analysis, and assessment, without mandating implementation choices or enforcing compliance. In EOSC-ENTRUST, this RMP defines the methodological approach applied within the project.
- **Requirements Repository:** a version-controlled repository used to store managed requirements, their metadata, and change history in structured formats. In EOSC-ENTRUST, this repository is implemented using Git and open, machine-readable formats such as JSON and ReqIF.
- **Stakeholder Requirement:** a requirement expressed directly by a stakeholder, reflecting needs, expectations, or constraints in the stakeholder’s own context and terminology. Stakeholder requirements are captured during elicitation and may be heterogeneous or overlapping prior to analysis.
- **Traceability:** the ability to establish and maintain relationships between requirements and their sources, related requirements, evidence, assessments, and external frameworks, supporting impact analysis and validation.
- **Validation:** the process of confirming that requirements and their supporting evidence adequately address stakeholder needs and intended use, typically involving stakeholder review and evidence-based assessment.

- **Verification:** the process of determining whether requirements are well-formed, unambiguous, and suitable for assessment. Verification focuses on requirement quality and verifiability rather than implementation correctness.
- **Verifiability:** a quality characteristic of a requirement indicating that it can be linked to one or more valid evidences.

Appendix B: Change Request Form template

This RMP proposes a Change Request template as part of the [5.6 Phase 6 - Change Control and Maintenance](#). It standardizes key details (affected requirement IDs, rationale, impact, and target version), to support efficient review and auditable traceability.

```
# Change Request (CR) Form

> Instructions:
> 1. Open a new issue in the repository hosting the requirements.
> 2. Use this template as the issue body.
> 3. Replace all placeholders with actual data.
> 4. The Change Request ID will be the Git issue number (e.g., `#123`).
> 5. Add any link using GitHub references (e.g., `REQ-001` or issue numbers).
> 6. Left empty the last part for reviewers

---

Change Request ID: `#` *(This will be auto-filled with the Git issue number once created)*

Requester: `Your name`

Role / Organisation: `Your role / team`

Affected Requirement ID(s):
- `R001`
- `R002`
*(Use requirement IDs or links to issues/pull requests if applicable)*

Change Type (select one):
- [ ] Clarification
- [ ] Scope adjustment
- [ ] Correction
- [ ] Dependency update
- [ ] Other (specify)

Description of Proposed Change:
*(Concise description of what is to be changed. Include links to requirements or related issues if possible.)*

Rationale:
*(Why the change is needed. Reference any discussions or issues.)*

Impact Analysis:

Impact on requirement intent:
```

```

*(Will the requirement purpose change?)*

**Impact on traceability:**
*(Will it break links to other requirements, tests, or documentation?)*

**Impact on evidence or assessments (if any):**
*(Does it affect verification, validation, or compliance evidence?)*

**Proposed Effective Version:**
*(Which version/release should include this change?)*

**GitHub Links:**
- Related issues: `#issue-number`
- Pull requests: `#PR-number`
- Requirements documents: `[REQ-001](link)`

---

**Reviewer(s):**
- `@Reviewer1`
- `@Reviewer2`

**Decision:**
- [ ] Approved
- [ ] Rejected
- [ ] Needs revision

**Decision Date:** `YYYY-MM-DD`

```

Appendix C: Reference Standards: mapping and structures

RMP Object (7. Data Model)	Mapping Type	Reference Standard	Technical Mapping / Direct Reference
Requirement	Format	ReqIF	<code>SpecObject</code> , a unique, versioned requirement entity identified with a persistent ID (<code>ReqIF.ForeignID</code>) for federated exchange (see full object structure at ReqIF Requirement Object).
Requirement	Metadata Attributes	ISO 29148	<code>System Requirement Specification (SyRS)</code> basic attributes: ID, Priority, Rationale, Source, Verification Method, etc. (see table 1)
Evidence	Conceptual Model	OSCAL	<code>observation</code> : Data, logs, or documents collected as proof, with a <code>relevant-evidence</code> that links back to a Requirement (see full object structure at OSCAL exemplary data objects).

Assessment	Conceptual Model	OSCAL	<code>assessment-results</code> : including the final "Pass/Fail/Partial" judgment and attributes like Assessor (Actor), Timestamp, and Validity Period (see full object structure at OSCAL exemplary data objects).
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ReqIF Requirement Object

At its core, a `SpecObject` consists of:

```

SpecObject
├── identifier (ID)
├── lastChange
├── longName (optional)
├── type (SpecObjectType)
│   ├── Attribute: ID (String)
│   ├── Attribute: Title (String)
│   ├── Attribute: Description (XHTML)
│   ├── Attribute: Priority (Enum)
│   ├── Attribute: Status (Enum)
│   └── Attribute: Source (String)
└── values (AttributeValue[])

```

ReqIF separates objects from relationships to support decomposition and mapping. A `SpecRelation` links two `SpecObjects`:

```

SpecRelation
├── source (SpecObject)
├── target (SpecObject)
└── type (SpecRelationType)

```

Where examples of `SpecRelationType` are `refines`, `dependsOn`, `derivedFrom` or `conflictsWith`.

OSCAL exemplary data objects

Control

The following snippet is a simplified OSCAL control expressed in JSON format illustrating conceptual alignment with OSCAL, a managed ENTRUST requirement such as “R048 – Minimum Security Baseline” could be represented in a structured control catalog format, including:

- unique identifier,
- normative statement,
- metadata properties (scope, origin, priority)
- optional parameters.

```

{
  "id": "R044",
  "title": "Standardised Data Access Request Mechanism",
  "class": "governance",
  "props": [
    {
      "name": "origin",
      "value": "ENTRUST MS8"
    },
    {
      "name": "domain",
      "value": "Access Governance"
    }
  ],
  "parts": [
    {
      "name": "statement",
      "prose": "The organisation shall implement and maintain a documented and standardised workflow for submitting, reviewing, approving, and tracking data access requests."
    },
    {
      "name": "guidance",
      "prose": "The workflow should support traceability of requests, decision rationale, and communication with requesters."
    }
  ]
}

```

Implementation object

Example conceptual implementation reference. This is equivalent to our “Evidence” object.

```

{
  "implemented-requirement": {
    "control-id": "R044",
    "statements": [
      {
        "statement-id": "statement",
        "description": "Access requests are processed via the federation portal integrated with the TRE ticketing system."
      }
    ]
  }
}

```

Assessment Result

Example conceptual assessment result. This is equivalent to our “Assessment” object.

```

{
  "assessment-results": {
    "assessment-result": [
      {
        "control-id": "entrust-r069",

```

```
    "finding": {
      "description": "Workflow engine operational and federation-compatible.
Sample execution validated."
    },
    "status": "satisfied"
  }
]
}
```